

TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATIONS AND AI IN LANGUAGE LEARNING AND COMMUNICATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15486419>

Annotation. This article is about Artificial Intelligence, how it works, and how this technology is currently being used in language learning. It presents thoughts and opinions on its effectiveness. The article also provides a detailed explanation of the advantages of using Artificial Intelligence technology in both learning and teaching languages.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence, language learning and teaching*

Introduction

Advances in technology have changed the way languages are learned and communicated. Nowadays, there is an AI and advanced technologies that provide new ways and solutions in these fields. This article discusses the impact of advanced technologies as well as AI on language learning and communication.

AI-powered apps like Duolingo, Babbel, and Rosetta Stone allow users to learn languages at their own pace. These programs analyze the user's skill level and then provide courses and tasks that are suitable for a learner. Through artificial intelligence, these apps identify the user's shortcomings and in turn, offer special suggestions to help them fix them.

The emergence of virtual and augmented reality technologies has expanded the scope of language learning. For example, VR allows students to communicate in a

foreign language in a simulated environment, which allows them to use the language more effectively and improve communication skills more than traditional language learning methods.

AI translation tools such as Google Translate and DeepL are convenient for language learning and communication. The real-time translation feature greatly increases productivity.

Voice assistants such as Siri, Alexa, Hey Cortana, Google Assistant and Hi Bixby based on artificial intelligence are used in language learning. They help users improve their speaking skills, learn grammar rules and expand their vocabulary. In addition, chatbots make language learning fun and effective by enabling real-time conversations.

Natural Language Processing (NLP) is a branch of AI that deals with the interaction between computers and human language. NLP technologies are widely used in language learning. For example, they can be used to automatically analyze texts, detect grammatical errors, and make suggestions for improving style.

AI has enabled the creation of personalized learning systems. These systems adapt lessons and exercises to each student's individual needs and learning pace. For example, AI identifies a student's weaknesses and provides customized learning materials to address them.

Through AI and big data analysis, trends and control in the language learning process are possible. Which methods will most effectively process such products into education and provide further training programs.

AI and technological innovations use gamification to make language learning more fun. For example, including points, completion of levels, and competitive elements increases student motivation to study harder.

Conclusion.

Technological innovation and artificial intelligence are creating new opportunities in language learning and communication. Applications based on artificial intelligence, VR/AR technologies, real-time translation, voice assistants and customized learning systems make language learning more effective, interesting and convenient. In the future, these technologies will continue to develop, making language learning and global communication even easier.

With the development of technology, language learning is not limited to textbooks and grammar rules. Instead, it has become an interactive, personalized and experiential process. It helps reduce the differences between languages and cultures around the world, fostering greater understanding and communication.

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